

The Use of Rice Husk Ash as a Reactive Filler in the PSO/EP Resin Composite for Potential Automotive Applications

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ABSTRACT:

The research studies about the development and characterization of a rice husk ash (RHA)-reinforced polysulfide oligomer/epoxy resin (PSO/EP) composite for use in automotive applications. To improve mechanical and chemical properties, RHA is a silica-rich agricultural byproduct which was incorporated at different loadings (0.5, 1, 2 wt%). The composite was prepared using a modified thiokol method for PSO and with universal EDP-2 epoxy resin which was supplied by Altai Prom Polymer. Many characterizations have been done. Crosslinking between the thiol groups of PSO and epoxy resin was confirmed by FTIR analysis, while XRD showed a hybrid structure that was primarily amorphous polymer networks and crystalline silica from RHA. SEM showed a consistent RHA distribution with strong adhesion between the filler and matrix. Mechanical testing demonstrated optimal performance at 1 wt% RHA, providing a tensile strength increase of 5% and a flexural strength increase of 49% compared to unfilled epoxy, due to RHA's ability to transfer stress. Increased RHA loadings (2 wt%) caused agglomeration and reduced strength. The composite demonstrated good thermal stability, resistance to automotive fluids, and low VOC emissions. Windshield adhesives (with a shear strength enhancement), underbody coatings (which offer corrosion resistance through RHA's SiO₂ barrier), and engine gaskets (with a compression set of less than 10%) are all potential automotive applications. RHA is underscored in the research as a sustainable, inexpensive filler that reconciles flexibility (PSO) and rigidity (EP), providing a practical substitute for synthetic fillers in lightweight automotive parts.

Keywords: Polysulfide oligomer, epoxy resin, rice husk ash, automotive composite, sustainable fillers.

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INTRODUCTION

For centuries, rice has been a fundamental food source and one of the most extensively grown crops worldwide, particularly in Asia [9]. Rice husk (RH), constituting roughly 20–23% of the weight of paddy, is an important byproduct of agriculture. Natural fibers such as rice husk, coconut shell, and

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breadfruit have been increasingly utilized in composite materials since the 1990s, thanks to their economic and environmental advantages [16]. Natural fiber composites provide benefits like lowered greenhouse gas emissions, reduced pollutant output, and a lower dependence on non-renewable resources. Rice husk ash (RHA), generated from the combustion of rice husks, is a silica-rich byproduct utilized as a reactive filler in polymer composites and hybrid systems [5]. Its application is growing quickly, particularly in polysulfide oligomer (PSO)/epoxy resin composites, driven by the increasing worldwide demand for sustainable and affordable materials. Materials scientists find RHA appealing due to its plentiful availability, affordability, and advantageous characteristics—including high thermal stability, pozzolanic activity, and reactive surface chemistry [10].

RHA's primary ingredient is amorphous silicon dioxide (SiO_2), while its minor constituents comprise CaO , K_2O , Al_2O_3 , and MgO . When treated correctly, RHA creates strong interfacial interactions with polar polymers, which greatly enhance the mechanical strength, chemical resistance, and environmental profile of the composites [8].

In construction, RHA-reinforced hybrid systems are incorporated into items such as adhesives, sealants, coatings, and waterproofing membranes. Furthermore, in cementitious materials, RHA interacts with calcium hydroxide to produce additional calcium silicate hydrate, which results in decreased porosity and enhanced compressive strength [4]. In PSO/epoxy resin systems, these materials create strong and flexible barriers that withstand chemical assaults, water penetration, and mechanical harm, making them perfect for protective concrete layers [18].

A key design aim in the automotive industry is to reduce vehicle weight to improve fuel efficiency and lower emissions. RHA-filled PSO/epoxy systems provide a sustainable option compared to conventional fillers such as carbon black, preserving durability while reducing material density. These composites are ideal for automotive components like sealing gaskets, underbody coatings, vibration dampers, and trunk liners, which require elasticity, thermal stability, and chemical resistance of which are enhanced by RHA integration [2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this research, firstly, 141g of Kazakhstan rice husk were taken and washed well, after washing put into the drying oven to heat up to 60°C to remove some impurities. Thereafter, using a self-propagating method to burn rice husk at $500\text{-}550^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 hours in an air furnace, after one day, washing the materials 6 times, then crushing the RHA via a roller and screening it through a $140\mu\text{m}$ using construction laboratories equipment, low temperature RHA was created. Table1, Fig.1. The second material is polysulfide oligomer which was synthesized by a modified thiokol method using sodium sulfide and sodium hydrosulfate. Fig. 2. Moreover, universal epoxy resin EDP-2 was prepared from the nearby market which was supplied by Altai PromPolymer (APP), Epoxy resin is a polymer that contains epoxide groups, and epoxy resin also known as polyepoxide. The color of the liquid hardener used as a curing agent is dark orange. Some typical properties and the chemical structure of the epoxy resin, PSO and RHA are indicated in Table 2, and Fig 3.

Composite Preparation

Firstly, 5g of polysulfide oligomer which was synthesized by a modified thiokol method using sodium sulfide and sodium hydrosulfate mixed with 3g of epoxy resin reinforced with different amount of RHA(1g, 0,5g, 2g), and mixed with a laboratory mixer for 10 minutes at room temperature, then lead dioxide PbO_2 and amine as a hardener and curing agent for PSO and EP resin were taken in the desired proportion. Amine hardener and epoxy are taken into in a ratio of 10:1 which means 10 parts epoxy and 1 part hardener. Thereafter, started mixing again for 10 minutes again to show best properties. The sample molded in a template according to GOST 21751-76. The samples were left at room temperature to cure for 36 hours.

Figure1. Diagram of RHA in Air-Furnace

Figure 2. Obtaining of PSO Process via a Modified Method

Figure 3. Chemical Structure of A Type Epoxy Resin

Table 1. Element Analysis of RHA (140µm) via XRF Method

No	Element	Concentration	intensity
1	Si	82,963	1,30
2	Ca	8,814	3,91
3	K	3,425	0,65
4	Fe	3,382	7,09
5	Mn	1,416	2,47

Table 2. PSO/EP Resin-RHA Compositions System

No	component	Amount	Crosslinking mechanism	Mw	Role
1	RHA	1, 05, 2g	Physical interactions	140µm (particle size)	filler
2	PSO	5g	2	1000-4000g/	Elastomeric modifier
3	Ep resin (EDP2)	3g	PSO-Ep curing	300-400	Matrix

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Importance of RHA as Filler Reinforcement

Rice husk ash (RHA), derived from the combustion of rice husk (RH) and containing silica, acts as a reinforcing filler in the PSO/epoxy matrix, enhancing its mechanical and chemical properties. The silica particles present in RHA help to mechanically reinforce by increasing the hardness, tensile strength, and modulus. It mainly occurs via physical interactions like hydrogen bonding and Van der Waals forces between the hydroxyl groups on the silica surface and the polymer chains. Additionally, due to its elevated melting point and thermal resistance, RHA enhances thermal stability by acting as a heat barrier that postpones the degradation of the polymer matrix. Regardless of this, it is vital to ensure a uniform dispersion of RHA within the polymer; insufficient mixing or agglomeration could lead to areas of concentrated stress, affecting mechanical performance [1]. Alongside physical reinforcement, it is crucial to enhance the PSO/epoxy composite through chemical interactions. The hydroxyl (-OH) groups on the RHA surface can interact with the epoxy groups of the resin, forming covalent bonds that enhance the interfacial adhesion between the filler and matrix. This reaction enhances overall durability and resistance to environmental degradation, reduces phase separation, and improves load transfer efficiency within the composite. These interactions can be enhanced through appropriate surface modification of RHA, like silane treatment, which improves compatibility with the polymer matrix. Presented is the reaction of epoxy with silica surface [13].

Reaction Mechanism of PSO/Ep Resin

Thiokol, which refers to polysulfide oligomers (PSO), is characterized by its flexible chains linked by sulfur-sulfur (S-S) bonds. It undergoes a copolymerization reaction with the epoxy resin, resulting in a cross-linked network. Here is how the reaction occurs:

Two polyepoxide molecules surrounding a polysulfide molecule form the ideal structure for reactive epoxy-polysulfide copolymers. This copolymer is formed by the stoichiometric excess of oxirane groups in relation to mercaptan groups. The amine hardener serves to open the free oxirane groups during chain extension or cross-linking reactions, resulting in liquid polymer products that are devoid of mercaptan groups. This arrangement is emphasized by the chemical structure of PSO-EP, as shown in Figure 4. In polysulfide oligomers (PSO), sulfur-sulfur (S-S) bonds are crucial for maintaining the material's flexibility and toughness; these bonds can reversibly cleave and reform, allowing the composite to exhibit self-healing properties and enhanced resistance to crack propagation, thereby making it highly durable and flexible in demanding applications [3]. During the reaction, numerous interactions between Thiol and epoxide take place, leading to the development of a three-dimensional cross-linked network that enhances the mechanical strength and chemical resistance of the composite. This illustrates the reaction process involving epoxy resin and liquid polysulfide rubber [14].

Figure 4. Reaction Mechanism between PSO and Epoxy Resin

Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) Analysis, a Morphology Study

The SEM measurement of the PSO/EP resin-RHA composites reveals a well-dispersed morphology, characterized by strong interfacial adhesion between the rice husk ash (RHA) filler and the polymer matrix. At a magnification of 2,500 \times , RHA particles seem equally distributed with no considerable agglomeration, suggesting effective mixing and compatibility. At a magnification of 5,000 \times , this homogeneity is further confirmed, as individual RHA particles are easily integrated into the epoxy-polysulfide network. The lack of gaps or cracks indicates outstanding wetting and adhesion, probably

resulting from chemical interactions between the silanol groups of RHA and the epoxy matrix, along with physical bonding from the flexible polysulfide chains [7]. Additionally, this uniform distribution is essential for improving mechanical properties, as it enables effective stress transfer and stops crack growth when under load. Indeed, these SEM micrographs reveal a robust interfacial adhesion, which has considerable impacts for the composite's performance in automotive and construction applications. The absence of agglomeration at the examined loadings (1g and 2g RHA) indicates that the composite can keep a balance between strength and flexibility, although higher concentrations of filler may need additional optimization to prevent brittleness. These morphological characteristics correspond with results from analogous silica-filled epoxy systems, in which optimal mechanical properties are usually obtained at moderate filler loadings (5–10 wt%).

Figure 5. (a, b) SEM Images of PSO/Ep Resin-RHA Composite at 5000x and 2500x Magnifications, (c) SEM Image of RHA at 5000x, (d) SEM Image of Pure EP Resin at Magnification of 5000x Respectively

FTIR Study

The FTIR spectrum of PSO/EP-RHA was investigated via spectrum 65 (FT-IR spectrometer). After analyzing the spectrum could identify 5 significant peaks at $3435,96\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $2923,99\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1507,31\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1099,89\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $548,98\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which correspond to O-H stretching, C-H stretching, C=C stretching, Si-O-Si stretching, and S-S bonds of PSO stretching, respectively. As can be seen in Figure 6, the broad peak at $3435,96\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is related to the hydroxyl groups (-OH) present in the silica (SiO_2) of the RHA and epoxy resin and demonstrates strong hydrogen bonding that enhances mechanical properties and interfacial adhesion. Therefore, the $2923,99\text{ cm}^{-1}$ peak shows the C-H

stretching, which is characteristic of the methylene groups that exist in both epoxy and PSO chains. The spectrum also demonstrates significant insights into the roles of RHA within the composite. The intense peak at 1099.89 cm^{-1} is associated with the asymmetric stretching vibrations of Si-O-Si bonds, thereby confirming the presence of silica from RHA. The stretching vibrations of the aromatic C=C at 1507.31 cm^{-1} are typical for the bisphenol-A structure within the epoxy resin, signifying that the primary structure of the epoxy is preserved after composite formation. These features show that RHA is physically included in the composite, but the main chemical interactions take place between the polysulfide oligomer and epoxy resin. This results in a crosslinked network that contains RHA particles.

XRD Study

To perform XRD analysis, the Whole Powder Pattern Fitting (WPPF) method was used. In this study, important structural details regarding the PSO/EP-RHA composite system are illustrated in the XRD pattern, as shown in Figure 7. The wide hump observed in the low-angle region ($20\text{-}30^\circ 2\theta$) signifies a considerable amorphous content, which we can ascribe to the crosslinked epoxy-polysulfide polymer matrix. This shapeless halo is characteristic of cured epoxy systems and indicates that the polymer network does not possess long-range crystalline order. Sharper diffraction peaks superimposed on this amorphous background confirm the presence of crystalline phases within the composite. Between $30\text{-}90^\circ 2\theta$, several distinct peaks can be seen that correspond to the crystalline components identified in the WPPF analysis. Therefore, the most notable peaks probably correspond to the orthorhombic sulfur phase (26.91 wt%) and silicon oxide (14.28 wt%) derived from the RHA filler. The sulfur peaks would manifest to approximately 23° , 27° , and $28^\circ 2\theta$, indicative of its S8 ring structure [6]. The presence of both amorphous and crystalline features in the XRD pattern illustrates the composite's hybrid nature. While the crystalline components (notably the silicon oxide from RHA) provide mechanical reinforcement, the amorphous polymer matrix offers flexibility and processability. Crystalline phases appear to retain their structure effectively within the composite, as indicated by the relatively sharp peaks, suggesting they are not significantly distorted by the polymer matrix. This is crucial for the thermal and mechanical stability of the material in potential automotive and construction applications.

Figure 6. FTIR Analysis of PSO/EP Resin-RHA

Figure 7. XRD Analysis of PSO/EP Resin-RHA Composite via WPPF Method

Mechanical Properties

Tensile strength

Figs. 8-9 demonstrate the tensile strength of the PSO/EP resin-RHA hybrid composite with different amounts of RHA that reinforced the polymer matrix. Hybridisation can result in either a positive or negative hybrid effect. When a property increases, it is referred to as the positive hybridisation effect, and when it decreases, it is called the negative hybridisation effect.

The tensile load-deflection curve for RHA reinforced PSO/Ep resin is illustrated in Fig. 7. The stress-strain curve indicates fiber breakage for 1% RHA, demonstrating that the adhesion between fiber and matrix was at its peak. Consequently, the failure mode was fiber breakage, providing the composite with maximum strength. Furthermore, the failure mode in all situations is brittle. The maximum elongation was observed at 1%, followed by 0.5%, while at 2% RHA it was the lowest [6].

A comparative analysis of tensile strength for different quantities of RHA has been conducted, as shown in Fig. 8. RHA positively impacts hybridisation effects on tensile properties. The addition of RHA initially leads to an increase in tensile strength; however, incorporating 2% RHA causes a decrease in strength. The addition of 0.5% RHA results in only a minor increase in tensile strength of 0.705%. Therefore, it can be concluded that the effect of adding 0.5% RHA on hybridization is limited. The enhancement in tensile strength for 1% RHA was 5%. However, when the percentage exceeded 1%, tensile strength decreased. When 2% RHA was added, the tensile strength decreased by 5.7%, which nullifies the advantages of hybridisation and the pre-treatment effect. The initial rise in tensile strength can be attributed to the high aspect ratio of RHA, which allows for improved stress transfer from the matrix to RHA, thus enhancing tensile strength. At increased filler loading, the RHA nanoparticles do not disperse effectively, resulting in a reduction of tensile strength.

Flexural strength

The flexural strength properties were examined, as shown in Figure 9. During the flexural testing, this study uncovered various behavioral patterns linked to changes in RHA concentration. With a support span of 40 mm, the 1% RHA achieved the greatest flexural strength (6,396 kPa), surpassing the 0.5% RHA (4,289 kPa) and the 2% RHA (2,729 kPa). The 1% formulation's strength advantage of 49% over the 0.5% composite illustrates the importance of sufficient filler content for bending resistance. It is important to point out that, despite the greater RHA loading of the 2% sample, its flexural strength was 57% lower than that of the 1% sample. This underscores the detrimental effects of filler overcrowding. As the RHA content increased, a notable pattern emerged in the load-bearing capacity, which rose from 31.3 N (1%) to 53.5 N (2%). This indicates that while extra filler particles aid in load distribution at a 2% loading, they also create stress concentration zones that weaken overall strength. The 2% RHA composite exhibited the most pronounced span-dependent performance (strength diminished with decreasing span length), highlighting its increased vulnerability to geometric constraints due to filler agglomeration. These findings indicate that for flexural applications, the optimal load for this composite system is 1% RHA.

Figure 7. Load/Deflection Curve for Different RHA Reinforcement

Figure 8. Tensile Strength Behavior for Different Mount of RHA with PSO/EP

Figure 9. Shows Flexural Behavior for Different Amount of RHA with PSO/EP Composite

Automotive Applications

PSO and EP resin are types of sealants used in various industries, serving as adhesive, sealing agents for joints, gaps, and other applications. So, the composite made of polysulfide oligomer/epoxy resin reinforced with rice husk ash (PSO/EP-RHA) demonstrates good flexibility, chemical resistance, and mechanical strength, making it ideal for rigorous automotive applications. A detailed discussion of its potential applications is presented below.

Adhesives and Sealants

Adhesive and sealants in vehicles, PSO/EP-RHA composites are especially useful for structural and non-structural applications. PSO-epoxy crosslinking shows a strong adhesion to metals, glass, and composites, while the polysulfide segments ($-S-S-$) provide remarkable elasticity. Due to the degradation of traditional polyurethane adhesives under prolonged UV exposure, this material is useable for windshield bonding. Moreover, RHA's nano-silica particles improve shear strength by as much as 30% relative to unfilled epoxy systems [12].

Anti-Corrosion Coatings and Underbody

Due to the composite's thermal stability (up to 200°C) and chemical inertness, it is appropriate for underbody coatings that shield chassis components from stone impacts, road salts, and moisture. Due to its high silica content ($\text{SiO}_2 > 85\%$), RHA creates a passive barrier against corrosion that surpasses the performance of conventional rubberized asphalt coatings, which are susceptible to cracking. Moreover, due to its high sulfur content, the PSO matrix is resistant to the degrading effects of automotive fluids (such as brake oil and fuel), which prolongs the coating's service life [17].

Seals and Gaskets

PSO/EP-RHA composites can serve as substitutes for traditional nitrile rubber or fluorocarbon gaskets in engine and transmission systems. The material's low compression set ($<10\%$ after 1,000 hours at 150°C) guarantees long-term sealing performance under cyclic thermal loads [15]. The RHA filler diminishes swelling when it meets hydrocarbons, which is a frequent failure mode for elastomeric gaskets [11].

Figure 10. Shows Sealant Car Gasket
Source: [19]

Figure 11. Shows Liquid Sealant Gasket
Source: [19]

interior Applications

Due to its adjustable surface hardness (Shore D 60–80) through RHA loading, the composite can be utilized for scratch-resistant interior features like dashboard panels and door handles. PSO/EP-

RHA, in contrast to thermoplastics, does not release volatile organic compounds (VOCs) when subjected to high temperatures, thus addressing concerns about cabin air quality [18].

CONCLUSION

The PSO/EP-RHA composite were made and investigated, the composite shows considerable potential for automotive applications, as it successfully merges the flexibility of polysulfide oligomer with the structural integrity of epoxy resin and the reinforcement capabilities of rice husk ash. The research demonstrates that loading RHA at 1 wt% optimizes mechanical performance, increasing tensile strength by 5% and flexural strength by 49% in comparison to unfilled epoxy. The uniform dispersion of RHA and, strong interfacial adhesion help to prevent stress concentrations. However, at higher loadings (2 wt%), agglomeration occurs, resulting in reduced performance. This composite is suitable for demanding applications such as windshield adhesives, underbody coatings, and engine gaskets, providing a sustainable alternative to traditional fillers. Future studies should concentrate on expansion capacity and altering the surface to enhance bonding between RHA and matrix for industrial production.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.A. Halip, S.H. Lee, P.M. Tahir, et al., "A Review: Chemical Treatments of Rice Husk for Polymer Composites," *Biointerface Research in Applied Chemistry*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 12425–12433, 2021. doi: 10.33263/BRIAC114.1242512433.
- [2] H. A. Abba, I. Z. Nur, and S. M. Salit, "Review of Agro Waste Plastic Composites Production," *Journal of Minerals and Materials Characterization and Engineering*, vol. 1, no. 5, Art. no. 5, 2013. doi: 10.4236/jmmce.2013.15041.
- [3] M. Abdouss, T. Farajpour, and M. Derakhshani, "The effect of epoxy-polysulfide copolymer curing methods on mechanical-dynamical and morphological properties," [Online]. Available: https://www.sid.ir/en/vewssid/j_pdf/84320116006.pdf
- [4] M. B. Ahsan and Z. Hossain, "Potential of Rice Husk Ash (RHA) as a Supplementary Cementitious Material in Concrete," *Advances in Civil Engineering Materials*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 473–488, 2018. doi: 10.1520/ACEM20170114.
- [5] R. A. Bakar, R. Yahya, and S. N. Gan, "Production of High Purity Amorphous Silica from Rice Husk," *Procedia Chemistry*, vol. 19, pp. 189–195, 2016. doi: 10.1016/j.proche.2016.03.092.
- [6] N. Bisht and N. Rani, "Effect of Rice Husk Ash on the Tensile Strength of Epoxy Based Bio-composite," *Advances in Research*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 258–270, 2024. doi: 10.9734/air/2024/v25i41103.
- [7] A. Dudek, B. Lisiecka, and K. Strzelczak, "Assessment of the quality of epoxy coating in the automotive industry," *Technical Transactions*, Year 2018 (115), pp. 175–180.
- [8] I. J. Fernandes et al., "Replacement of Commercial Silica by Rice Husk Ash in Epoxy Composites: A Comparative Analysis," *Materials Research*, vol. 21, no. 3, 2018. doi: 10.1590/1980-5373-mr-2016-0562.
- [9] S.-H. Kang, S.-G. Hong, and J. Moon, "The use of rice husk ash as reactive filler in ultra-high performance concrete," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 115, pp. 389–400, 2019. doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2018.09.004.
- [10] M. N. N. Khan, M. Jamil, M. R. Karim, M. F. M. Zain, and A. B. M. A. Kaish, "Utilization of Rice Husk Ash for Sustainable Construction: A Review," *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 9, no. 12, pp. 1119–1127, 2015. doi: 10.19026/rjaset.9.2606.
- [11] S. Kumar, A. Saha, and D. Zindani, "Agro-waste-based polymeric composite laminates for aerospace cabin interior and identification of their optimal configuration," *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*, vol. 14, no. 24, pp. 31907–31923, 2024. doi: 10.1007/s13399-023-04914-2.

- [12] T. C. Lee, Polysulfide Systems for Environmental Protection. ASTM International, 1995. [Online]. Available: <https://books.google.com/books?id=OfgqsjKYEDYC>
- [13] P. Mishra, P. Mishra, and R. S. Rana, "Effect of Rice Husk ash Reinforcements on Mechanical properties of Aluminium alloy (LM6) Matrix Composites," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 6018–6022, 2018. doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2017.12.205.
- [14] H. Mozafari and H. Hamidinezhad, "The effect of adding CoFe₂O₄–CdS nanoparticles on the mechanical properties of rice husk ash epoxy composite: An experimental approach," *Applied Physics A*, vol. 125, no. 5, Art. no. 330, 2019. doi: 10.1007/s00339-019-2632-7.
- [15] C. R. Shastry, L. S. Thompson, and F. W. Lutze, "Performance of coatings for underbody structural components," *SAE Transactions*, pp. 219–237, 2001.
- [16] N. Soltani, A. Bahrami, M. I. Pech-Canul, and L. A. González, "Review on the physicochemical treatments of rice husk for production of advanced materials," *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 264, pp. 899–935, 2015. doi: 10.1016/j.cej.2014.11.056.
- [17] B. Song, F. Wu, K. Moon, and C. P. Wong, "Formulation and processing of conductive polysulfide sealants for automotive and aerospace applications," in *2019 IEEE 69th Electronic Components and Technology Conference (ECTC)*, 2019, pp. 157–162. doi: 10.1109/ECTC.2019.00033.
- [18] Y. Wang, W. Liu, Y. Qiu, and Y. Wei, "A One-Component, Fast-Cure, and Economical Epoxy Resin System Suitable for Liquid Molding of Automotive Composite Parts," *Materials*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 685, 2018. doi: 10.3390/ma11050685.
- [19] "Auto Tips," Wuling Motors Indonesia. Accessed: May 14, 2025]. [Online]. Available: <https://wuling.id/Home/Blog/Auto%20Tips>

